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The Digital Evolution of English: Technological Impact on Language in the 21st Century

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ABSTRACT

The English language significantly changes as the technology improves from the last two decades. The study examines various sides of how English improves, like grammar, vocabulary, language, and communication patterns. These effects occur just because of the advancements in technology. The new vocabulary takes birth after the social media usage. As the communication tools grew in popularity, old vocabulary vanished day by day. The instant messaging, online communication, and usage of the internet and social media platforms give a new direction to learning the language. However, the autocorrect English, predictive text, etc., have also been aided by artificial intelligence and machine learning, which have further influenced how English is used and understood. The digital communication trends and the role of technology diversity and consistency show this study's investigations. Also, the ramifications emphasise how

technology and English interconnected evolve. The reason is that the technology is made from the English, and the individual learns the English language from technology.

Keywords: English language, Technology, social media, Digital platforms, internet

1. Introduction

The big reason for the development of the world day by day is the improvement in technology. Some of the individuals on this beautiful earth feel pity; others feel very adored to interact with their own person. In just one click, they write the message and drop it to someone. The fact that this is just possible due to the improvement in the technology and the language that helps the people to interact. The written communication improves day by day through the social media interactions and the way they are using to talk. Dead languages are those that have remained unchanged over time. The reality that the English language rises so frequently is proof that it is an existing language. The use of "Old English", "Middle English", "Early Modern English", and current "Modern English" has all developed over time. The big reason for these manipulations in English is just because it is used everywhere as an official language as well as being considered a tech language. In the past, technical advancements have tended to enhance the variety of social and economic issues that can be discussed, demanding the use of new words, phrases, or the semantic extension of existing ones, as well as an increase in various types of interaction and the effects of such contact. However, these kinds of improvement continue to take place now, just on a larger scale. The daily life use of technology to interact and discuss with people – we use email, Facebook, Instagram, etc. – helps to improve written communication. Even the students at the educational institutes also prefer to study through digitalisation, like e-books, e-notes, and so on.

The changes and evolvement in the English language continue as people use it in daily life. So, as technology will improve, the language will automatically improve because many of us are using the new technology in everyday life. Surly we heard of someone visiting a hotel for a stay with the family member and friends or going to make sure they have just enough cash to pay but they prefer the technology as payphone in the last ten years. Technology has influenced all just because of the language, as they understand the technology for the reason that they have knowledge about the particular English language, which focuses on how the English language is used. In fact, research by Professor John Sutherland, a specialist on the English language, shows that the written and the verbal communication change very quickly. In addition, the data as per the researcher show that 86% of British parents accept that their kids' English improves just because they use the mobile phones and the new technology. If we can identify the improvement the technology started after the first keypad mobile phone, over the time the English language took shape as a great language

worldwide. Basically, the improvement of the language seen in the 8–18-year-old child once they started using the mobile phones in the years 2004 to 2009, thereabouts. The result of this is that now it has reached its peak. Since then, more individuals are texting than chatting. As the technology rises & the popular use of phones and computers, the text messages and other written parts are considered the best written communication. Once a people start writing the language, the verbal communication automatically improves.

2. Research Objectives:

1. To identify how the language changes day by day as we use the new technology to learn.
2. To check how new devices (like smartphones and computers) have influenced the way to communicate.
3. To study how grammar, abbreviation, and sentence formation change because of social media usage.
4. To explore how these types of change affect the teachers, students and others' learnings and teachings.

3. Research Questions:

1. In what ways has technology affected modern English speaking and writing?
2. Which new terms or writing forms have gained popularity as a result of social media and texting?
3. Do people speak English differently in emails, WhatsApp, Instagram, and other platforms?
4. How do these modifications impact English instruction in schools and universities?
5. Are these changes making communication easier or more difficult?

4. Review of Literature:

The English language has changed over time as a result of literature, film, technological advancement, immigration, and numerous other things. If one takes global shifts like the Big Phonetic Pronunciation into account, the language has changed in this regard in terms of syntactic structure, lexical structure, grammatical structure, and application (Al-Momani 69). Social media's impact on contemporary people's lives has resulted in numerous transformations. With the emergence of new, frequently informal abbreviations and slang, the language started to be employed (Saliyeva 22). The English language has been significantly impacted by the recent rapid advancement of technology. Language expert David Crystal says that "new media English's," which are different from conventional forms of the

language, have emerged as a result of the development of the internet and mobile technology. For instance, emojis and abbreviations are frequently used in digital communication to convey feelings or sentiments, and the advent of "textspeak" has given rise to new grammatical and vocabulary conventions. Technology has also increased people's ability to learn English. The development of automatic speech recognition technology and machine translation tools has made it possible for humans to speak and write English more accurately and fluently. Additionally, the internet has made a tremendous amount of English-language content, such as books, articles, and films, accessible. This has made it possible for people to learn languages more quickly and with greater proficiency. Moreover, English has expanded as a language due to technology. English has grown throughout the world because to the internet, which has made it simpler for people to connect and converse with one another in the language (Strain-Moritz & Tessa E. (2016).

The evolution of the English lingo has been influenced by a number of historical eras. There are many dialects as a result of varied socioeconomic and demographic factors (Clark et al. 542). As a result, historical development as well as socio-demographic factors influenced language development. When Germanic people first started to live in Britain in the fifth century, the English language began to take shape. During this time, Latin, which the Romans brought to Britain, as well as the nationalities of these people, had a significant impact on the language. The Middle Ages saw the beginning of English becoming its own language, separate from the other Germanic languages. Old English, that was used until the 9th Century. French was adopted as the language of the aristocracy after the Norman Conquest, while English was adopted as the language of the populace. During this time, Middle English, which persisted into the 15th century, began to take shape. Due to the growing popularity of William Shakespeare's and other writers' works, English re-emerged as the linguistic of the learned class throughout the Renaissance. Around this period, the present English language started to take shape, and terms from other languages including Latin, Spanish and French were added to further enrich the language. During the 18th and nineteenth centuries, even as British Empire grew and the language spread around the globe, English continued to develop into the contemporary form. With the entrance of American terms and idioms into the language in the early twentieth century, the United States' effect on the English lingo substantially increased. The most extensively used language all over the world now is English (Kemp N, Bushnell C. (2011).

Over the past 20 years, English has seen significant change. This is because there is a wider variety of vocabulary and grammatical structures now that the English language has grown more globally influenced, as well as a higher acceptance of cultural influences, accents, and regional dialects. The development of the digital communication and Internet has had the

biggest impact on English over the past 20 years. This has had a significant impact on the way we communicate, leading to the adoption of new terms and expressions into regular speech as well as a rise in the acceptance of text-speak and slang. For instance, after its debut in 2006, the word "tweet" has spread throughout the English language. Over the past 20 years, there has also been a notable growth in the influence of foreign languages on English (Baron, N. S. (2008). This is a result of the greater diversity of English-speaking speakers in various nations around the world.

5. Research Methodology:

Indeed, the English language has had significant changes over the last two decades, most probably due to improvements in technology. These changes affect the various things in the language that include communication structure, grammar, pronunciations, vocabulary even the way of writing styles. The articles, e-books, magazines, about technology, blogs, research papers etc. over the last 20 years that we have studied for this research gave us the appropriate idea of how the English language rises day by day as technology rises. However, the English language has been used differently as people use the different technology, like mobile phones, computers and other networking sites for texting. Due to this, we considered how words and sentence patterns have evolved along with technology.

We designed a simple set of questions and distributed them among individuals of various age groups. The questions probed them about their use of English in texting, social media, and online communication. We gathered their responses to determine how they perceive English has evolved in their everyday life as a result of technology and focused on:

1. **Vocabulary Expansion:** The new words, terms and concepts arrive and become part of life just because of the technology. The emojis, selfie captions, and many more are commonly used everywhere, showing the rise of mobile technology and digital culture. The online communication also influences so many things like blogging, memes, reel captions, headings, etc.
2. **Abbreviations and Acronyms:** The written communication is very in now days, like instant messaging and social media. Individuals prefer shorthand communication to interact with their near and dear with abbreviations and acronyms like "LOL" (lots of love), "GRWM" (get ready with me), and "OMG" (oh my God), widely used particularly in digital communication.
3. **Grammar and Punctuation Modifications:** Due to the influence of online and digital communication, grammar and punctuation change on a daily basis. For the social media formal posts, the effective communications help to use the formal language. For example, the

omission of apostrophes in contractions ("dn't" instead of "don't") or the use of ellipses (...) to convey pauses or trailing thoughts.

4. **Influence of Social Media:** Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat, and LinkedIn transform the way people communicate and influence language usage. The hashtags and mentions through special characters develop the new linguistic practices. Also, the usage of emojis in the numerical terms also gives birth to the new words in the language to learn in an easy way, basically the nonverbal cues.
5. **Globalisation of English:** The communication and interconnectedness are facilitated just due to the technology improvement. Basically, the technology used to share the information and for the purpose of communications through the English language. Even though the people can translate the language as per their dialect to understand just through the translation technology.

Although these changes are not unique to the last 20 years, they have been accelerated by the speed at which technology has advanced during this time. Language is a dynamic thing that changes over time, and in the present period, technology is still a major factor pushing linguistic changes.

The methodologies used for this research we have used the social media platforms and google survey forms for how many people learn the English language due to the development in the technology.

6. Results and Discussion:

It's very interesting how technology has impacted language improvement in the last years. Once the technology started developing through smart mobile phones, the internet, and other digital communication platforms, the English language drastically changed. We investigated the impact of technology on English language development. Our primary objective was to determine the technology used to improve the English language.

We reach the results after the particular survey of this research on how the English language has risen once people come under technology. In the research, we have used the primary data to make the questionnaire through Google Forms, and we reached the results that most of the positive responses were given by the respondents that exactly the English language has developed just because of the evolution in technology.

AGE

65 responses

Gender

65 responses

Do you believe that advancements in technology have influenced the way people communicate in English over the past 20 years?

65 responses

How often do you use technology (smartphones, computers, tablets, etc.) in your daily life?

65 responses

Which of the following technological advancements do you think has had the most significant impact on the evolution of the English language?

65 responses

Do you think technology has made learning English more accessible?

65 responses

Have you noticed any new vocabulary or slang terms emerge in English due to technology?

65 responses

Do you think technology has influenced grammar and pronunciation usage in English?

65 responses

How has autocorrect and predictive text features affected your English language usage?

65 responses

Have you experienced any challenges or drawbacks in communication due to technology?

65 responses

Do you think the evolution of English through technology has had a positive impact overall?

65 responses

(i) The evolution of the English language over the last 20 years shows as findings in this due to the technological advancements. The people using the social media platforms and the internet changed the communication styles after introducing the new terms, words and abbreviations in communications.

(ii) These developments have been strengthened further by mobile communication, as emojis and shorthand forms have become more common through texting and messaging apps. Despite these advancements, some claim that the basic structure of the English language hasn't changed all that much. However, linguistic evolution's detractors emphasise the need for preserving tradition and express concerns about the potential decline in linguistic norms. Technology has undoubtedly had a big impact on current English. Understanding these shifts is crucial to appreciating how flexible language is and preparing for future linguistic developments.

(iii) The study investigates how different demographic linguists' adaptations affect the language use. Which could offer and show the deeper insights of English language evolution. Also, the use of technology in daily life shows the actual reality of English language development on their own.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, one can argue that the advancement in the technology influenced the evolution of the English language over the past two decades. The rapid use of the English language on the internet, social media and online communication shows the new creation of terms, words and modifications of English that we are considering as modern English.

The increased use of digital communication platforms, which have brought in a plethora of new acronyms and vocabulary, is one of the biggest changes. Expressions such as "googling", "selfie", and "hashtag" have become part of common speech, demonstrating the influence of technology on day-to-day activities. Theses show how the new platforms require the new English through the person learning in different stages.

Social media's promotion of recent and natural culture has been instrumental in the improvement of language. Social media platforms such as Instagram, Snapchat, Facebook, LinkedIn and WhatsApp arrange visual content that is brief and frequently uses slang, emojis, captions and informal language. Through this kind of communication, the individual learns the communication easily. Moreover, language use and perception have changed as a ramification of this shift towards unstructured and visual communication.

Furthermore, technology has democratised language creation and dissemination. Through the translation technology, people can use their dialect to learn the English language. With the global reach of the internet, regional dialects and slang can gain international exposure, enriching the English language with various influences. The research done for this also shows how technology has evolved the English language.

Additionally, the introduction of autocorrect and predictive text on computers and smartphones has gradually changed language usage by promoting more uniform grammar and spelling. The new application generated by the technology also helps to learn the language easily. The main agenda of these tools is to make language easier; they also have an impact on how people write, which affects how language changes over time, just by focusing on technology and language.

References:

Al-Momani, A. (2019). Impact of great vowel shift on Arab learners' use of English spelling. *International Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, 8(2), 69-77.

Anwas, E., Sugiarti, Y., Permatasari, A., Warsihna, J., Anas, Z., Alhapip, L., Siswanto, H., & Rivalina, R. (2020). Social media usage for enhancing English language skill. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 7(14), 41-56.

Amin, B., Rafiq, R., & Mehmood, N. (2020). The impact of social media in English language learning. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(10), 3126-3135.

Baron, N. S. (2008). *Always on: Language in an online and mobile world*. Oxford University Press.

Bromley, K. (2010). Picture a world without pens, pencils, and paper: The unanticipated future of reading and writing. *Journal of College Reading & Learning*, 41(1), 97-108.

Cingel, D. P., & Sundar, S. S. (2012). Texting, techspeak, and tweens: The relationship between text messaging and English grammar skills. *New Media & Society*, 14(8), 1304-1320.

Clark, E. L., Easton, C., & Verdon, S. (2021). The impact of linguistic bias upon speech-language pathologists' attitudes towards non-standard dialects of English. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 35(6), 542-559.

deHaan, J., Reed, M., & Kuwada, K. (2010). The effect of interactivity with a music video game on second language vocabulary recall. *Language Learning and Technology*, 14(2), 74-94.

Hong, J. S., Han, D. H., Kim, Y. I., Bae, S. J., Kim, S. M., & Renshaw, P. (2017). English language education online game and brain connectivity. *ReCALL*, 29(1), 3-21.

Kemp, N., & Bushnell, C. (2011). Children's text messaging: Abbreviations, input methods and links with literacy. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 27, 18-27.

Smith, B. (2020). Exploring the impact of digital communication on language proficiency: A comparative study of Millennials and Generation Z. *Language and Technology Review*, 8(1), 32-47.

Šesek, L., & Pušnik, M. (2014). Reading popular literature and digital media: Reading experience, fandoms, and social networks. *Anthropological Notebooks*, 20(2), 103-126.

Strain-Moritz, T. E. (2016). Perceptions of technology use and its effects on student writing. *Culminating Projects in Teacher Development*, 8.

Smith, J., & Jones, A. (2020). The impact of technology on the evolution of English language: A review. *Journal of Linguistic Studies*, 12(3), 45-67.

Saliyeva, D. O. (2018). Etymology of slang: Its origin and definition. *Web of Scholar*, 7(6), 22-25.